

Impact of Mobile Phones on Socio-economic Life of Working Women Living in Slums of Delhi

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Abstract

In recent past with the diffusion of information technology, the application of mobile phone users in all strata of society increased with rapid speed. The study is synced to trace the implications of use of mobile phones by the poorest and largely illiterate household working women (maids) living in pathetic conditions of slums in Delhi city on their social and economic life. Apart from tracing the demographic structure of their family it is to examine the level of awareness due to the use of mobile phones. The study is aimed to establish the linkage between literacy rate and utility of mobile phones among the women.

The mobile phone once reached in the hands of the economically dependent women of partially literate section which is largely belongs to immigrant families and living in highly vulnerable, insecure and unhygienic condition brought significant change in women empowerment. Use of mobile phone become instrumental for generating awareness about rights of women, competitive wages, increased income, efficiency of working conditions, economic and social security in society. The study established the linkage of use of mobile phone and its heterogeneous parameters of women emancipation of household working women those are living in slums and illegal colonies.

Keywords Digital Exclusion, Underprivileged Women.

Introduction

Digital Exclusion of Underprivileged Women: Gendered Social Benchmark

A basic level of usage and assimilation of digital services by women over men has been a strong point of discussion in all strata of society with several surveys and research data suggesting the same. Gender inequality already existing at a great level in India further deepens this digital divide and all over the country only one third of the users are women. Dwelling into this trend for rural women reveals that embracing this technology poses greater challenges than their urban counterparts. The level of awareness and opportunities offered by mobile internet usage are fewer in case of rural women, as well the fact that the costing of smartphones or internet enabled handsets is more and as a result not affordable. This is a direct consequence of lower incomes in slum areas leading to lesser digital literacy and hence less consent to pay for these smartphones.

Objective of study

The study is based on primary data generated through the employers of household working women and living in slum habitations of Delhi to address the following objectives:

1. To examine the social and demographic fabric of household working women residing in slums or squatter settlements.
2. To establish the linkage between literacy rate of household working women and application/use of mobile phones.
3. To trace the relationship of use of mobile phones and its impact on the socio-economic condition of household working women living in slum habitations.

Review of Literature

Gender gap in access to technology

As India is making its way to the top developing nations of the world, an issue that still cripples the country is gender inequality. The technology boom post COVID has benefitted the population world over but a gender inequality still exists for its access to females being less than male counterparts. The lack of gender parity in usage of digital modes of communication are hindering the access to its benefits to women inhabitants of slum areas. Traditional gender roles in our society dictate males as the bread earners and females as homemakers and in many slum areas, women are restricted to even use any mobile phones in their day-to-day life for a fear of getting too much exposure to the outside world.

Many surveys have been carried out to assess the impact of mobile phone usage in rural areas and its direct/indirect impact on their socio-economic growth [Jain & Sarin, 2009; Velayutham, C. et al. 2024; Rahman, Md A. et al. 2023]. Data released by the Annual Status of Education Report (ASER 2023: Beyond Basics; a citizen-led household survey that provides a snapshot of the status of children's schooling and learning in rural India) in New Delhi on 17 January 2024 revealed that females were less likely to use a smartphone compared to males. The data collected showed that males (43.7%) are more than twice as likely to have their own smartphone than females (19.8%) [https://asercentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/ASER-2023-press-release1_English_16-Jan.pdf]. Unfortunately the decision of owning a digital device in a home is also dictated by the man of the house [<https://www.hindustantimes.com/technology/only-31-women-own-mobile-phones-says-oxfam-report-on-india-digital-divide-101670317918778.html>].

However, use of low-cost mobiles holds a promise to connect women of slum areas to their social contacts, family members beyond the city they are residing in and also an exposure to the job market. Economic independence is of great importance in contemporary society as it would allow them to contribute to the finances of the household as well. This would lead to their increased participation in the modern economy of our developing nation. A survey of household helps residing in slums and unplanned habitation setups was done to determine their digital literacy and knowledge of how their economic independence may grow if they are exposed to the opportunities offered by the same.

Significance of Study

The transformational possibilities of smartphones are now evident in places where there are development needs and there is an established link between smart technology and economic progress. In India the mobile has transformed from being an elite device to a mode of necessity and communication among the marginalized population. However, we still have minimal information about the actual use of this new technology by the 'non elite strata' and their changing view of this wide world obtained by the use of technology. This study was carried out among female domestic helps (maids) those are living in the slums of Delhi. Around more than one third of the total population of Delhi (2.18 crore) lives in slum. The social media is constantly highlighting the use of new technology and how it is contributing to the growth of various business. This is in line with the development based policy of 'Digital India'. But most of these studies are limited to certain sections of the society.

The study emphasize on the penetration of the smartphones in the marginalized women section of our society residing in slums. Here we present the accounts of smartphone usage by women domestic help who are slum dwellers. The primary question being addressed the impact of usage of mobile in the socio-economic life of women domestic help living in the slums of Delhi. The domestic help represent doubly marginalized section; first being slum dwellers and second because of their weaker gender being women.

Methodology

A organized questionnaire-based demographic survey was carried out reaching to respondents through their respective employers in the form of structured interview in

Hindi as their vernacular language. The respondents are women residing in slums habitations and working as domestic help within the radius of 5 km. from their residence. The respondents are from heterogeneous socio-cultural and linguistic background in the age group varying from 18- 60 years living in slums of Delhi-NCR. In many cases they could not tell their precise age due to lack of official documentation, so their approximate age was recorded. Since most women were illiterate, their verbal consent was taken and they were assured of anonymity.

The interview was carried out by the employers by asking a set of structured questions. The interview was carried out in informal and participatory method to trace the real observation. The women were also observed in their usual and normal work surroundings for over a period of time. We understand that the data collection process can be affected by the fact that the interview was conducted by each of the different employers and the bond shared between the employer-employee. The interviews often lasted for very short period due to the hectic schedule the domestic help needed to adhere to moving from one house to another. Sixteen questions through the questionnaire were asked which included questions sharing their personal details, marital status, number of children, literacy and how procurement of a smartphone has affected their social awareness, income status and health conditions of their family members. Graphs were constructed based on the percentage of responses received for each question and data was interpreted and discussed.

Result and Discussion **Demographics**

Age Structure

The distribution of age among respondents highlight a diverse demographic. The largest age group is represented by the age category of 35-45 years, making up 38.9% of the participants. This is followed by women aged 25-35, who constitute 30.6% of the sample. Women aged 45-55 account for 13.9%, while both the youngest group (18-25 years) and the oldest group (55+ years) each make up 8.3% of the respondents. This distribution indicates a broad spectrum of ages, potentially offering varied perspectives on how technology influences different stages of life.

Place of Birth

The survey included a heterogenous population of women from different places of birth all over the country. Majority of these rural women are from rural landless communities of Uttar Pradesh (27.8%), Delhi (19.4%) and Bihar (11.1%). Many respondents were hiding to disclose their birth places as it carry social stigma of poor region of India.

Primary Residence

A majority, 51.4%, reside in unplanned settlements, highlighting the prevalence of informal housing lacking basic infrastructure and services. Resettlement colonies and villages each account for 20% of the respondents, indicating a significant portion lives in more structured, albeit still challenging, environments. A smaller group, 5.7%, lives in temporary slum clusters, and 2.9% reside in squatter settlements, both of which are typically characterized by extreme poverty, pathetic living condition and instability of stay.

Living in unplanned and squatter settlements of temporary structure of approximately 10 feet by 10 feet hutments often means dealing with inadequate access to utilities such as electricity, water, and sanitation, which makes technology’s enhancement of their incomes all the more necessary and impactful on their lives. These environments may also be prone to evictions and lack legal protections, adding to the residents’ vulnerability. Understanding the distribution of primary residences is crucial to analyzing technological solutions that cater to the specific challenges faced by women in these diverse living conditions, ultimately helping to improve their quality of life and socio-economic opportunities.

A significant 58.3% of the women live in rented houses without any documentation while 38.9% of the respondents own their homes. For the majority who rent, the financial pressure of regular rent payments and potential instability due to the risk of eviction or rent increases underscores the significant financial challenges these women face.

Marital Status

A substantial majority of responding women, 63.9% are married, data from whom will be telling of technology’s impacts on their family’s lives. The 11.1% of unmarried women represent a smaller segment, potentially highlighting different social and economic challenges they face independently. Meanwhile, the 25% of widowed respondents suggest a considerable portion of the sample may be dealing with additional burdens of financial and social support in the absence of a spouse. This varied marital status

distribution suggests that technology's impact may differ greatly based on familial and social contexts, influencing the study's results on how technology aids these women in their daily lives.

The distribution of ages at which respondents were married provides important context for understanding the impact of technology on their lives. A significant 45.2% of women were married between the ages of 14 and 18, indicating early marriage is prevalent among this demographic structure. This is followed by 32.3% who were married between 18 and 22, suggesting that a substantial portion still married relatively younger. A smaller group, 12.9%, married even earlier, between 10 and 14 years old. Only 9.7% of respondents were married at age 22 or older.

Early marriage often results in limited educational attainment, as young girls are typically withdrawn from school to assume domestic responsibilities. This interruption of gender specific girl child school dropout in education can lead to reduced literacy rates and fewer employment opportunities, perpetuating a cycle of poverty and dependency. Furthermore, early marriage often brings early motherhood, which can pose health risks for both the mother and child, and increase the financial burden of childcare at a young age. This distribution highlights the likelihood of early marriage influencing educational and career opportunities, which could, in turn, impact how these women utilize and benefit from technology.

Number of Children

With 33.3% of the women having three children and 19.4% having four or more, a substantial portion of the respondents are managing large families. This high number of dependents can strain financial resources, particularly in low-income settings like slums. The 22.2% of women with one child and 13.9% with two children still experience financial pressures, though likely to a lesser extent. Meanwhile, 11.1% of women with no children might face fewer immediate financial responsibilities. Women with larger families often encounter higher expenses related to food, clothing, education, and healthcare for their children. With such financial demands, the role of technology in enhancing these women's income and bringing material change to their lives proves all the more important.

Other Relevant information from the participants

Literacy Status

The literacy distribution among respondents in the study underscores significant educational disparities that influence the impact of technology in their lives. A substantial 34.2% of the women are illiterate, representing a major barrier to accessing and benefiting from technology. Those with education up to the 5th grade constitute 31.6%, indicating that nearly two-thirds of the respondents have very basic or no literacy skills. Only 13.2% have studied up to the 8th grade, and 7.9% up to the metric level (10th grade). A mere 2.6% have completed 12th standard, while 10.5% have pursued education up to the postgraduate level.

The high rates of illiteracy and low educational attainment suggest that many women in this demographic composition may struggle with using technology effectively, as digital literacy often requires a basic level of reading and comprehension skills. This educational gap can limit their ability to leverage technology for personal, educational, or economic development, perpetuating the cycle of poverty. For those with minimal education, technology that includes user-friendly interfaces, visual aids, and vernacular language options could be more accessible and useful.

Time of Smartphone Procurement

The distribution of when respondents acquired their smartphones highlights varying levels of familiarity and experience with technology. A significant portion, 33.3%, obtained their smartphones 4-6 years ago, indicating a moderate level of experience and adaptation to digital tools. This is followed by 27.8% who acquired their devices 2-4 years ago, suggesting they are relatively new to the smartphone landscape but likely comfortable with basic functions and apps.

Interestingly, 13.9% of respondents got their smartphones less than 2 years ago, pointing to a growing trend of recent adoption, possibly driven by increased affordability or the recognition of the benefits of connectivity. Another 13.9% have had their devices for 6-8

years, reflecting a long-term engagement with technology, while 8.3% have been using smartphones for 8-10 years. Only 2.8% have had their smartphones for over 10 years, representing early adopters who might have a significant depth of experience. This distribution suggests that while many women have had smartphones long enough to integrate them into their daily lives, there is still a substantial portion relatively new to these devices.

Procuring A Smartphones and Its Economic Correlates

A significant 61.11% of respondents reported that smartphones primarily increased connectivity, highlighting the device's role in facilitating communication and networking opportunities. For 22.22%, smartphones enabled receiving online payments, streamlining financial transactions and potentially expanding income-generating capabilities. Additionally, 19.44% mentioned that smartphones increased awareness of job opportunities, underscoring their role in accessing employment information and job market dynamics. A smaller percentage, 2.78%, noted that smartphones enhanced awareness of competitive rates for work, suggesting a niche but impactful benefit in optimizing income generation. However, a notable 25% of respondents indicated that smartphones did not enhance their income. This could stem from various factors such as limited access to digital platforms for income-generating activities, inadequate digital skills to leverage smartphone capabilities effectively, or economic barriers that restrict the full potential of smartphone use for income enhancement.

Social Security Owing To Use Of Mobile Phone

The role of smartphones in enhancing women's social security reveals significant reliance on connectivity for various support networks. An overwhelming 88.89% of respondents

highlighted smartphones' role in rapidly connecting them with family members, underscoring the device's crucial role in maintaining familial support and safety networks. Additionally, 52.78% mentioned using smartphones for quick connectivity with employers, suggesting its utility in professional communications and job security. For 38.89% of respondents, smartphones facilitated rapid communication with friends, social workers, and other support networks, enhancing their social safety net beyond immediate family.

However, only a small percentage, 2.78%, mentioned using smartphones for connectivity with police or security apps, indicating a less prominent role in direct security enhancement through law enforcement channels. These findings highlight smartphones' pivotal role in enhancing social security through improved communication and access to support networks. Initiatives that promote digital literacy and awareness of safety apps could further empower women to leverage smartphones for enhanced personal security.

Enhancing Social Awareness

Majority of respondents agreed that they have an increased social awareness due to being active on various social media apps including Facebook and Instagram. Around 44% users said that they were dependent on SMS for any updates. 22.22% respondents used the search engine to browse information and 11.11% browsed the mobile news. This data shows that social media platforms remain a popular choice among women of slum areas.

Ownership/Usage of Social Media Accounts

A substantial 69.44% reported using YouTube, indicating a prevalent interest in video content consumption, educational resources, and entertainment. Facebook follows with 30.56%, serving as a popular platform for social networking and community engagement. WhatsApp, used by 13.89% of respondents, plays a crucial role in instant messaging and group communication, facilitating both personal and professional interactions. Instagram, with 16.67%, is utilized for sharing photos and videos, reflecting a growing trend in visual storytelling and personal expression. In contrast, LinkedIn, at 2.78%, caters more to

professional networking and career development. Interestingly, 13.89% reported not using any of these apps, potentially indicating limited access to or interest in digital platforms, or preferences for other forms of communication and information consumption.

Material Empowerment of Women Due To The Usage Of Mobile Technology

The material changes in women's lives resulting from enhanced income through smartphones highlight varied priorities and improvements in household welfare. A significant 38.89% reported using increased income to support their children's education, emphasizing the importance placed on educational opportunities as a pathway to future stability and success. Nearly as many, 36.11%, used the additional income to purchase household necessities, underscoring the immediate impact on improving living conditions and basic amenities. A smaller yet notable 11.11% indicated renting a better home, suggesting a desire for improved living standards and stability. Similarly, another 11.11% purchased a two-wheeler, potentially enhancing mobility and access to economic opportunities such as commuting to work or expanding business activities. These changes reflect how smartphones empower women economically, enabling them to make meaningful investments in education, household welfare, and mobility. Such financial improvements not only enhance immediate living conditions but also contribute to long-term socio-economic mobility and empowerment.

Use of Mobile Phone Correlated With Health Benefits

The role of smartphones in ensuring better health conditions for their families is significant, with various ways these devices contribute to healthcare access and awareness. A substantial 44.44% of respondents reported that smartphones helped them find and access government medical facilities, highlighting their role in facilitating access to essential healthcare services. Additionally, 16.67% used smartphones to locate and access medical facilities in private hospitals, indicating a broader spectrum of healthcare options available through digital means. In cases of emergencies, 36.11% utilized smartphones to quickly contact medical facilities, underscoring their critical role in timely

medical intervention. For ongoing healthcare management, 8.33% stayed connected with medical practitioners through digital communication platforms, enhancing continuity of care and access to medical advice.

Furthermore, 13.89% mentioned that smartphones raised awareness of health issues, suggesting their role in disseminating health-related information and promoting preventive care practices. However, 19.44% reported no change in their healthcare practices due to smartphone use, which may reflect challenges in accessing or utilizing digital health resources effectively. These findings highlight smartphones' potential to improve healthcare access, information dissemination, and emergency response capabilities among women in under served communities.

Conclusion

The answers to the above mentioned questionnaire reveals several key points of the demographics of rural women that impact their access to digital media. Living in low quality households with difficult access to basic amenities for a living leads to an unstable life with more financial pressure. A major chunk of our participants have been married at an early age which led to burden with domestic responsibilities and fewer employment opportunities. High rates of illiteracy also suggest that there is a struggle with use of technology effectively and this drawback prevents them from owning any device that may seem like a burden.

The access to digital media is definitely a big step in the future to economic independence and social security but it comes with its own set of challenges the biggest being online safety [<https://www.downtoearth.org.in/governance/girls-in-rural-india-less-likely-to-know-how-to-use-smartphones-computers-survey-93960>].

The high rates of illiteracy and low educational attainment suggest that many women in this demographic may struggle with using technology effectively, as digital literacy often requires a basic level of reading and comprehension skills. This educational gap can limit their ability to leverage technology for personal, educational, or economic development, perpetuating the cycle of poverty. For those with minimal education, technology that includes user-friendly interfaces, visual aids, and vernacular language options could be more accessible and useful. The trend in rural areas is to have larger family setups with more expenditure in education, clothing and healthcare facilities.

Given such monetary demands of the day, digital access will open more doors in boosting family incomes and transforming the lives of women. Use of mobile phones made the working women able to explore more paying job for less working hours so they may use the saved time for the job in another house which resulted into increased income. The purchase of bicycle or scooter further boost the working opportunity contemplating to increased income. Mobile phones are not only made the working women from slum habitation more mobile and migratory but also resulted the social upgradation and economic self sufficiency bypassing the dependency on male counterparts.

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